

Analysis for LHC experiments at CERN

Dirk Duellmann, Bernd Panzer-Steindel, Markus Schulz,
Andrea Sciabà, David Smith

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1 Motivation and goals

Physics analysis is done at CERN by hundreds of physicists in a variety of ways, using all kinds of hardware resources and software tools, with an ever expanding set of methods. Running interactively on very large collections of data has become possible and dedicated resources were deployed for this purpose, with Machine Learning and new columnar data formats becoming more and more popular.

The purpose of this work is to help determining the most effective approach for the CERN IT department to improve the way computing resources dedicated to analysis are organised and provided, taking into account new forms of analysis and examine whether they can be adequately supported by CERN possibly in novel ways (a natural candidate being a dedicated analysis facility). The scope of this investigation is the preparation for the LHC Run 3 and the ATLAS and CMS analysis use cases.

We begin with an overview of the resources currently available for analysis and their utilisation levels, followed by detailed performance studies, with a special focus on CPU efficiency and storage and network I/O in a variety of hardware configurations, an examination of EOS logs to extract usage patterns and finally an assessment of the available options.

2 Current analysis resources

Analysis is currently performed using several resources and entry points, in a way that is largely dependent on the type of analysis and the personal preferences of users and user groups. We can classify them in three main categories:

- Grid resources
- Batch resources
- Interactive resources

Various monitoring systems allow to quantify the usage levels of different resources, which in turn is important to understand their relative sizes and ultimately plan for their evolution. Grid resources should be considered out of the scope of this investigation, as on this respect CERN is just “another” WLCG

Experiment	Completed jobs	Running jobs	CPU time	Wallclock time
ATLAS	100000	2500	70 years	80 years
CMS	600000	8000	140 years	170 years

Table 1: Approximate job statistics for ATLAS and CMS Grid analysis jobs at CERN during a period of seven days. All jobs use a single process/thread.

site and they are already optimised for Grid analysis. Batch and interactive resources allow for a much higher degree of customisation: GPU-enabled nodes have recently become available and ARM-equipped nodes are foreseen in the coming months. Usage of Grid resources during a period of seven days for ATLAS and CMS is summarised in table 1.

Batch resources are used also via direct job submission to HTCondor to the LXBATCH cluster. As there is no easy way to disentangle analysis jobs from other types of jobs, one can only put an upper limit to the amount of resources used by analysis by looking at the monitoring data. As an example, the resources used by ATLAS and CMS in a period of seven days amount to averages of 4400 CPU cores and 8800 CPU cores respectively, with peaks up to 3-4 times the average.

Finally, a variety of interactive resources exists. The LXPLUS service is the “mainstream” option. Again, it is difficult to know which fraction of tasks performed are analysis tasks, but in average over a period of seven days ATLAS and CMS users received around 100 and 70 CPU cores respectively.

SWAN is another interactive service that can be used to run analysis tasks in Jupyter notebooks. An estimation of the resources utilised by SWAN users is not directly available from monitoring systems, but it was estimated by parsing the logs of production nodes to calculate the total amount of wallclock time of running containers by experiment. For ATLAS and CMS and a period of 10 days this amounted to about 8500 and 16000 hours \times cores respectively, of which only 5% see any actual computation (the rest is idle time).

The usage of the Spark/YARN clusters was similarly computed for a period of 10 days. After excluding contributions that are known not to be physics analysis, the ATLAS usage was about 18500 hours \times cores and the CMS usage was 22000 hours \times cores.

A last category of resources includes special high performance nodes made available to the experiments, in amounts of a few units for experiment and each node having two CPUs with 32 physical cores.

The conclusion of this overview is that, currently, the vast majority of analysis at CERN is done on the Grid or on LXBATCH, while interactive analysis is a very small fraction of the total. This is already a preliminary indication that any special analysis needs (in other words, not yet covered by the Grid or LXBATCH) could be easily satisfied by diverting a relatively small fraction of the overall analysis resources, if needed. The question is then to identify such needs and the best way to satisfy them.

3 EOS log file investigation

This section summarises the analysis described in detail in Appendix A. The goal was to determine, by using information in log files from EOS and the batch system, if data access patterns from batch analysis suggest ways to improve the efficiency of access to EOS data.

After excluding “production” users and selecting only users who read a large amount of data (more than 100 TB from February to May 2021), it is assumed that the remaining users ($O(100)$ for both ATLAS and CMS) are mostly doing analysis (table 16). The distributions of the file access rates (Fig. 12-13) show that only a very small fraction of about 1% of the file reads exceeds the capabilities of a HDD and thus relies on the server memory cache. Moreover, the measured I/O speeds are largely below the capability of EOS (as measured by a trivial benchmark reading random files from EOS). Despite a high number of file re-reads, it seems fair to conclude that an attached extra HDD-based file cache would not bring any benefits in terms of performance.

Measurements of the actual file opens per second and seeks per file similarly show that typical values are rather small (less than 20 file opens per second and 10 seeks per file), very comfortably within the limits for EOS.

Even extrapolating at the HL-LHC scale, the number of required spindles should only double, as should the maximum I/O per spindle. The total I/O throughput would be of the order of 1 TB/s.

In conclusion, there seems to be no performance bottleneck at the storage level even for the “power users”; no performance enhancements nor additional layers are needed and there is a significant headroom to cope with increased demands. It is worth reminding here though that the bulk of these statistics consists of batch analysis jobs, which are mostly Grid jobs.

4 Tests of XCache using example analyses

This section summarises a series of tests and measurements performed on two test XCache instances using different client applications.

In order to understand the demand created by different analysis workloads on storage systems, solid state device (SSD) and rotating disk (HDD) based test infrastructures have been built. The performance characteristics of these systems have been first measured using a highly flexible stress test system, MockData [1]. MockData tests were run in such a way as to achieve saturation in terms of I/O operations or throughput of the infrastructures under investigation. These measurements provide estimates of the maximum achievable capability of a given setup.

In a second set of measurements, example analysis workloads from ATLAS and CMS have been used to observe the individual I/O metrics of the workloads when using with different types of storage.

4.1 Hardware

A list of nodes with some details of the hardware and the configuration of various systems can be found in table 2.

Host	CPU	RAM (GB)	Storage	Network (Gb/s)
xcache01	2× Intel Silver 4216@2.1(32 core / 64 HT)	192	96× 12 TB HDD (1152 TB)	25
xcache02	2× Intel Silver 4216@2.1(32 core / 64 HT)	192	96× 12 TB HDD (1152 TB)	25
xcache03	2× Intel Gold 5218@2.3(32 core / 64 HT)	192	16× 1.92 TB SATA SSD (30.7 TB)	25
xcache04	2× Intel Gold 5218@2.3(32 core / 64 HT)	192	16× 1.92 TB SATA SSD (30.7 TB)	25

Table 2: Hardware configurations of the test nodes; HT stands for hardware threads. All machines are running CentOS 7.

xcache01 and xcache02 are recent disk servers, each configured with 96 12 TB HDD and a 25 Gb/s network interface. The HDD are attached via SATA to an LSI SAS3216 I/O controller running via PCIe v3 ×8. Since a limiting factor of these links is the PCIe portion, the expected maximum aggregate data rate to the disks should be at most 7.88 GB/s per server. A test consisting of reading from all disks with *dd* gave a rate of 6.67GB/s. xcache01 and xcache02 represent nodes found at the Tier-0, the Tier-1 and possibly some Tier-2 sites.

Similarly, the xcache03 and xcache04 disk servers have recent CPUs and 16 1.92 TB SATA SSD attached to an LSI SAS3516 I/O controller running via PCIe v3 ×8; therefore a similar maximum aggregate data rate due to the PCIe link of about 7.88 GB/s per server is calculated. A test of reading from all disks with *dd* gave a rate of 6.99GB/s. These nodes are candidates for either high performance front-ends for storage services, or building blocks for analysis facilities.

A diagram of the network topology is shown in Fig. 1. The figure illustrates the situation for the HDD based test Xcache, but the arrangement for the SSD cache is similar. The node type of the clients and source nodes are not given here, most were virtual machines provisioned via openstack. Their use is described in more detail in section 4.2.

4.1.1 Hard Disk Drive based XCache

Figure 1: Diagram illustrating the nodes involved in the test HDD Xcache. The two disk servers forming the test XCache service are each connected with 25 Gb/s interfaces to the network. Other nodes labeled as source and client are used in some tests and are connected at 10 Gb/s. The source nodes can add 20ms to the request latency to emulate the impact of nodes located remotely.

In order to establish coarse grain performance, random reads against individual disks were performed to measure the achievable IOPs for a random access pattern (the expected lowest IOP value). The *fiio* tool was used to read 32 KiB sized blocks at random positions from the 12 TB disks (Toshiba brand, model *MG07ACA12TE*). In this configuration, 218 IOPs could be achieved. The sequential read rate was also measured at various offsets over the disk, using *dd* with a block size of 10 MiB. The estimated average rate over the whole disk was 200 MB/s. Table 3 lists the number of random reads per second over different offset ranges on the disk and the sequential read rate achieved at different offsets.

TB	IOPs	MB/s
12	218	128
10	228	164
8	243	193
6	261	214
4	293	229
3	298	238
2	317	246
1	349	253
0.5	361	253

Table 3: Performance of an individual disk when only using limited space, measured as random read operations per second (IOPs) and sequential read rates (MB/s) at different positions on the drive (TB).

For the SSD-based systems, the *fio* and *dd* measurements have not been carried out yet, due to a lack of time. However, when running the *high seek job* of MockData, roughly 4500 IOPs per SSD could be observed, with a system load of about 30% .

4.2 Baseline tests

The tests described in this section are intended to put a realistic read load on the XCache instances using MockData, with the purpose to investigate stability of operation and to quantify a baseline performance.

In order to confirm that the setup was working, we did an initial run using a component of MockData called *randomreader*. The setup consisted of five client nodes and the HDD-based XCache instance. By running 32 processes on each of the client nodes, each one reading large blocks (128 KB) mostly sequentially, about 5 GB/s could be achieved (Fig. 2). The aggregate network bandwidth of the client nodes is 5×10 Gb/s and matches that of the two XCache nodes, equivalent to a data rate of 6.25 GB/s. Since this is noticeably higher than the rate measured by *randomreader*, there is some suspicion that the rate was limited by the number of clients. In order to prevent this, we used eight client nodes in subsequent MockData tests.

Figure 2: *randomreader* clients running on five nodes sending requests to a 2-node, 192 HDD XCache. The top plot is the average CPU utilisation and the bottom plot is the combined network interface utilisation across the two nodes. The read load consists of 128 KiB requests, 99% of which are sequential.

For most of the subsequent tests, we used the main MockData components, *loadgenerator* and *coordinator*. Load on the XCache instance is generated by a number of distributed *loadgenerator* processes, using the standard xrootd C++ client library, XrdCl. During the test, a *coordinator* process sends details of transfers to the *loadgenerators*. These transfers are based on the actual files and open times from a six-month period of ATLAS data processing in 2018 at the Prague Tier-2. The list corresponds to 1.5 PB of file reads, for a total file size of 438 TB.

A transfer job can be configured in different ways for what concerns the file read timings:

- Original timings: for example, if the second file was originally opened 10 seconds after the first, in the test the second file is accessed 10 seconds after the start of the test.
- Scaled timings: for example, in the previous case and with a scale factor of 2.0, the second file is accessed 5 seconds after the first file.
- Target rate: the original ordering of the file opens is retained but the start times are ignored. File accesses are started to reach an overall target read rate. Such target rate can be set to be fixed, or to linearly increase over time up to a desired maximum value.

If an individual MockData file transfer job cannot be completed within the targeted time it is considered overrunning and will eventually be cancelled after a preset overrun factor.

In this section, most of the tests use a predefined target rate (either fixed or increasing with time). The file access pattern, the read rate and the total amount read from individual files are fixed parameters and are independent of the aggregate target rate.

The details sent to a *loadgenerator* process include file name, file size, and how much of the file and with what parameters the file should be read. The filename has significance in that files are cached in the Xcache based on the

file path. The files in the MockData test are not real data files stored in a storage system, but they are generated on the fly by on the five “source nodes” described in Fig. 1 and having similar specifications as the eight client nodes already described. The files have a deterministic content that can be cross-checked by the client to check for delivery errors.

As noted in the Fig. 1 the “source nodes” also have functionality to introduce a latency, but the use or testing of this feature is not discussed further.

Tests which are described as *high seek rate* are based on ATLAS MC pile-up jobs, i.e. event mix, digitization and reconstruction workload, whose main parameters are shown in table 4. Seek distance and read request size were generated according to the tabulated mean and a measured frequency distribution, supplied as input as histogram entries.

Average read size	24.7 KB
Data read-factor	3.05
Probability of seek per read	80%
Seek distance as fraction of file	0.0007
Target read rate per file	6.67 MB/s

Table 4: Parameters used for the *high seek* runs of MockData, based on an ATLAS pile-up job from 2018. The seek distance for an average sized datafile was 760KB.

Several test runs were made with the *high seek rate* access pattern, with the objective to find if there is a limit on the aggregated read rate below the network interface limit.

Figure 3: *loadgenerator* clients running on eight nodes replaying a file list using the *high seek rate* access pattern, directing requests to a 2-node, 192 HDD XCache instance. The top plot is the average CPU utilisation and the bottom plot is the combined network interface utilisation across the two nodes. The test targeted a network rate of 5 GB/s but this was not reached.

The tests were run with partially populated caches. Fig. 3 shows a constant rate test which was targeting 5 GB/s. It can be seen the the achieved rate was below 2 GB/s for most of the time. In Fig. 4 two runs are shown, targeting a linearly increasing rate, up to 2 GB/s.

Figure 4: *loadgenerator* clients running on eight nodes replaying a file list using *high seek rate* access pattern, directing requests to a 2-node, 192 HDD XCache. A first test is started with a target rate from 500 MB/s to 2 GB/s over 30 hours. Some files are in the cache, some not. A second test is started with a target rate from 1.25 GB/s to 2 GB/s over 15 hours using only files already in the cache. The top plot is the average CPU utilisation and the bottom plot is the combined network interface utilisation across the two nodes.

We then performed tests that model the use case of staging data on the client node with *xrdcp*. In this scenario, complete files are sequentially read with large block sizes (2 MB). For this test, additional client machines have been added to match the bandwidth of the XCache system. By doing this, 300 concurrent jobs configured to maximise individual data rate could be supported. This corresponds to 5 transfers/sec.

In order to study a potential way to accelerate the access to a large scale HDD-based system (like EOS), a load-balanced SSD-based XCache instance has been setup using *xcache03* and *xcache04*. The rates achieved when running a *high seek rate* Mockdata test are shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5: *loadgenerator* clients running on eight nodes replaying a filelist using *high seek rate* access pattern, directing requests to a 2-node, 32 SSD XCache. The top plot is the average CPU utilisation and the bottom plot is the combined network interface utilisation across the two nodes.

Baseline values

The MockData runs described previously are used to make some estimates for data rates that the Xcache could support. The values are shown in table 5. Two methods were tried to find the estimates. In one method, MockData tests are made targeting various rates and the point at which some of the transfers start to overrun gives an estimate. Another method was to observe the average network rate that could be seen when a high target was set. The latter estimate is higher than the former. Table 5 shows both ifnbnmj available.

Storage Type	Access Pattern	Rate (overruns) (GB/s)	Rate (net monitoring) (GB/s)
HDD	Sequential	5.5	6.0
HDD	High seek	1.2	1.7
SSD	Sequential	-	~6
SSD	High seek	-	~6

Table 5: Baseline performance of HDD and SSD 2-node XCache instances for sequential and random type loads as seen during MockData tests. Estimates were made of the rate when tests start to overrun their target duration, while the other estimate is based on the observed network traffic from network monitoring.

On reproducibility of results

Mockdata runs are not reproducible at the connection or packet level. This is due to both the implementation and the nature of interaction with a storage system. Mockdata uses a list of files and progresses through them in strict order; however there are various sources of variation, some which could be eliminated and some could not. The sources include:

- Variation in response timings from the server;
- the parameters of individual file access requests are generated randomly from a frequency distribution. The seeds of the generator are not reproducibly set and would quickly become de-synchronised because the same generator is shared between different files;
- in the MockData target rate mode, the timings of transfers depend on the observed rate of completion of recent files. The exact rate of completion of recent files depends on the internal state of the storage system and a variety of other factors;
- the concurrency level of requests will be determined by the actual performance of the storage system. i.e. if requests are serviced slowly but submitted at a predefined rate the concurrency will rise. At some point resources would be exhausted and transfers must be terminated in a non-reproducible way.

MockData was originally a tool to test the caching behaviour and stability of Xcache, and so the file names, size and order of file access are as much as possible honored with respect to an input reference list. Additionally, MockData is intended to generate a load that approximates the overall read traffic received by a storage system from a Tier-2, and less priority was placed on the reproducibility of individual requests.

Notwithstanding the above points, the results observed are expected to be reproducible. It is acknowledged that ranges, such as standard deviations or interquartile-range might make the presented work more complete and could be measured in the future.

4.3 Realistic analyses and their data

In order to have a better idea of data access performances under realistic conditions, experts from ATLAS and CMS provided us with three sample analysis jobs using the experiment software frameworks and corresponding input datasets. The analyses are shown in table 6.

Name	Experiment	Version	Data	Events
top-xaod	ATLAS	AnalysisBase / 22.2.48	one DAOD_PHYS file	35000
cms-skimmer	CMS	CMSSW 10.2.13, vbsH- wwSkimModule of PhysicsTools	640 NANOAOOD- SIM files	$6.7 \cdot 10^8$
aggregate gradients	CMS	root v6-25-01- 906-g1f1e9b8	189 root files	-

Table 6: Three types of analysis.

4.3.1 Job description and running methodology

The hardware used for the analysis jobs is not quite the same as discussed in the baseline discussion of section 4.2. In the present discussion only the XCache nodes are used. For one of the analysis jobs the client machines used in 4.2 have insufficient RAM, which forced us to also make use of the XCache hardware for running the test analyses.

For tests targeting an HDD-based XCache the analyses are run on one of the SSD XCache nodes, and vice versa. For *local* tests the analysis jobs are run on a node that has the SSD or HDD directly attached and file access is used, not network access. For runs described as *EOS based* the analyses are run on one of the XCache nodes, but use EOS as a data source.

The jobs are run in such a way as to try to fully utilise the CPU on the execution node. Only the *aggregate gradients* job actively uses multiple threads while performing the analysis, while in the *top-xaod* and *cms-skimmer* jobs only a single thread is doing most of the work and they are considered single threaded jobs. In case the jobs produce output during execution, this is temporarily stored on a local SSD different than those storing the input data. The jobs were run as follows.

The *aggregate gradients* test is a root script and it reads 189 input files with a total size of about 1.5 TB. The script has a startup time during which it allocates about 90 GB of RAM and initialises it. The job then has a period where it reads and processes the input data. Finally there is a writing phase during which a results file is written. It is the same analysis which was previously presented as a benchmark and labelled as a *tight selection of tracks* [2].

The analysis script was already instrumented to measure the time elapsed for reading and processing. Tests showed that the initial and final steps were largely single threaded (elapsed-time ~ 700 seconds, CPU/elapsed ~ 1.1). The reading and processing step aims to use all 64 available hardware threads and it is the time and CPU efficiency of this step which are considered of interest in the current study.

After this benchmark was first introduced, the EOS team found a setting to improve performance in the form of an environment variable setting for the client [3]. Most of the results presented in table 7 include this setting, which is indicated by *env* in the configuration column.

Further investigation done for the this paper led to another client-side optimisation for this benchmark, which allowed the exploration of even higher data rates. The setting is labelled as *multi conn* in table 7. This corresponds to the effective change shown by the diff output in listing 1. The reason for performance increase with this change is discussed further in section 4.5.

```

! std::string filename = "root://host//path/globalcor_*.root";
! ROOT::RDataFrame d(treename, filename);
—— 1,5 ——
! TChain tchn(treename.c_str());
! tchn.Add("root://t000@host//path/globalcor_0_1.root");
! tchn.Add("root://t001@host//path/globalcor_0_2.root");
! [...]
! ROOT::RDataFrame d(tchn);

```

Listing 1: Aggregate gradients: illustrative diff file for *multi conn* used in some tests

Configuration	Devices	Rate (GB/s)	CPU eff (%)	active devs (%)	rreq/s/dev	MB/s/dev	kB/rreq	util (%)
Local filesystem	1 HDD	0.15	2.38	100	346	181	523	99.9
Local filesystem	96 HDD	4.2	45.0	53.6	77.7	40.6	524	20.5
Local filesystem	16 SSD	5.5	61.5	92.5	567	297	524	55.3
XC, env only	96 HDD	0.21	5.95	32.3	4.23	2.21	523	1.06
XC, multi conn	96 HDD	2.5	28.8	56.7	47.6	24.9	524	14.0
XC, env only	32 SSD	0.90	10.5	87.5	53.0	27.7	522	5.34
XC, multi conn	32 SSD	2.8	32.6	89.5	187	85.5	446	17.0
XC, multi conn, no env	32 SSD	1.9	20.8	79.7	121	55.1	455	11.0

Table 7: Results for the *aggregate gradients* job. Configurations are shown for local file systems and XC (XCache). Rate is dataset size divided by the elapsed time during the analysis step; CPU efficiency uses the total CPU time minus an estimated CPU time spent in initialisation and finalisation; the device activity is for a sub-period inside the analysis step of the job. The jobs in the third row ran on a 2.3 GHz CPU, all others on 2.1 GHz CPUs.

The *cms-skimmer* analysis reads a number of input files and writes an output file. A sample of 640 NANOAODSIM files was used, for a total size of almost 1 TB and containing 670 million events. The job script sets up a CMS working area and builds the PhysTool component from source, linking against the CMS framework via CVMFS. The job then processes one input file, using only one thread, and 64 jobs are started under PrMon [4] to fully use the CPU. Each job processes a different file and new jobs are started each time one finishes. Since the input files are of varying sizes the jobs do not all end at the same time.

The *top-xaod* analysis reads an input file and writes an output file. Only one distinct input file was used, containing 35000 events for a size of 1.16 GB. Since the job is practically single threaded, the input file was copied 256 times and 64 concurrent jobs were run under PrMon. As jobs finish new jobs are started. To avoid most jobs ending at the same time each job was set to process a random number of events between 1 and 35000.

The *top-xaod* workload included a systematics setting which can be set to *Nominal* or *All*. The latter reduced the data read rate by an order of magnitude, but the results presented in this document correspond to the Nominal setting.

4.4 Description of the measured quantities

In this subsection the quantities presented in tables 7, 8 and 9 are described.

Configuration	Rate (MB/s)	CPU eff (%)	active devs (%)	rreq/s/dev	MB/s/dev	kB/rreq	util (%)
EOS, Nominal	-	99.0	-	-	-	-	-
XCache HDD, 2 nodes	13.6	99.3	16.9	0.338	0.137	406	0.0787
XCache SSD, 2 nodes	13.0	99.5	70.3	1.91	0.781	404	0.162
Local filesystem, 16 SSD	-	99.5	92.6	4.18	1.76	421	0.386

Table 8: ATLAS *top-xaod* job results. The configuration of the data source is shown along with the measured values. The configuration in the third row ran on a 2.1 GHz CPU, all others on 2.3 GHz CPUs.

Configuration	Rate (MB/s)	CPU eff (%)	active devs (%)	rreq/s/dev	MB/s/dev	kB/rreq	util (%)
EOS	92.8	76.0	-	-	-	-	-
XCache HDD, 2 nodes	93.0	81.4	35.2	6.04	0.938	155	1.41
XCache SSD, 2 nodes	95.5	81.5	64.1	60.7	2.43	40.0	0.932
Local filesystem, 16 SSD	-	92.4	100	91.8	12.3	135	3.72

Table 9: *cms-skimmer* job results. The total amount of data read at network interface for remote access was 337 GB. The configuration in the third row ran on a 2.1 GHz CPU, all others on 2.3 GHz CPUs.

The *configuration* columns describe the conditions for the analysis execution. This includes the data source, which in many cases is one of:

- an XFS filesystem or set of filesystems locally mounted on the machine running the jobs. Each file system is on a separate device, SSD or HDD. The machines and devices are the same used for XCache in other tests;
- an EOS project area accessed with xrootd via the XrdCl client;
- an XCache, with is either the SSD or HDD based one, described in section 4.1. In some tests either one or both the 2-node systems are involved and the number is indicated by the number of HDD or SSD. The XCache is always "warm", i.e. all the required files were already entirely present in the cache and spread over all involved storage devices at the file level, i.e. each file on exactly one disk.

The network *Rate* is intended to indicate the rate at which input data is being processed by the analysis. For the *top-xaod* and *cms-skimmer* jobs, the rate is the combined rate of all 64 running jobs and is measured by considering the number of received bytes at the network interface of the machine running the jobs. As described in section 4.3.1, at the end of these runs there will be a period of draining where fewer than 64 jobs run. This period is not included. The rate is calculated over an ad-hoc period during which 64 jobs should be running.

For *aggregate gradients* the rate is derived from the dataset size divided by the elapsed time of the reading phase, as reported by the job script. The data received at the network interface was 1.60 TB and the database size is 1.54 TB, which is thought to be consistent with all the data being read.

The *CPU efficiency* is an extension of the CPU/wallclock time. For *top-xaod* and *cms-skimmer* the user+system time is summed up over all the individual

jobs and divided by the sum of the elapsed times. For *aggregate gradients* the situation is complicated by the significant elapsed and CPU time spent during the initialisation and finalisation steps, where no data are being read. Equation 1 was used to assign a CPU efficiency to the processing portion of the job.

$$\epsilon_{\text{CPU}} = \frac{t_{\text{CPU}} - 1.1(t_{\text{wall}} - t_{\text{processing}})}{64t_{\text{processing}}} \quad (1)$$

where ϵ_{CPU} is CPU efficiency, t_{CPU} is the reported user+system time, t_{wall} is the overall elapsed time for the whole job, $t_{\text{processing}}$ is the elapsed time reported by the job for the reading and processing portion.

The *active devs* metric is the fraction of storage devices (HDD or SSD) being used by the test which were active within a 1-minute interval, averaged over the duration the sample. Active means at least one read request was issued.

The *rreq/s/dev* is the number of read requests issued per second per device averaged over all storage devices. The requests are those from the block layer and do not necessarily correspond to the size or number of the requests that the user layer issues in `read()` or similar calls.

The *MB/s/dev* is the number of megabytes read per second per device.

The *kB/rreq* is the average size of issued read requests in kilobytes.

Finally, *util* is the device utilisation in percent, averaged over all the storage devices. The device utilisation is the fraction of time during which at least one operation is outstanding to the device. Storage devices will likely be able to queue multiple requests concurrently and may be able to process them concurrently.

The block-device read-ahead for both HDD or SSD devices in the XCache instances was left at its default value, which was 4 MiB in all cases. The *deadline* I/O scheduler was used for the HDD and SSD block devices.

4.5 Discussion of the results

Overview

The three analyses shown in table 6 cover a range of input rates, due to their inherent processing and data needs. Two of them, *top-xaod* and *cms-skimmer*, are single thread jobs, while the *aggregate gradients* job automatically uses all the cores of the client machine. Therefore in *top-xaod* and *cms-skimmer* test runs, a number of copies is used to fill all the CPU cores in the system.

Ranking the jobs by data rate, *aggregate gradients* achieved more than 5.5 GB/s, followed by *cms-skimmer* at 95.5 MB/s and finally *top-xaod* with 13.6 MB/s.

A more detailed discussion of the results is given in the rest of this section.

Aggregate gradients

The highest CPU efficiency for this test was 61.5% and was obtained when using 16 local SSDs, whose average utilisation was 55.3%. It is assumed that if the limiting factor was the storage or CPU the disk utilisation or CPU efficiency should approx 100%, respectively. The bottleneck limiting this case has not been

identified. The observed read rate of 5.5 GB/s is about 79% of the observed maximum read rate of 6.99 GB/s (see section 4.1).

Considering the cases where data are accessed via the xrootd protocol (EOS or XCache) the impact of the two client-side settings described in 4.3.1, *env* and *multi conn*, is seen to be important. For a given configuration the impact of varying the two settings was seen as: 0.90 GB/s (*env* only), 1.9 GB/s (*multi conn* only), 2.8 GB/s (*env* + *multi conn*). The latter is approaching the limit of the network interface of the machine.

The effect of the *multi conn* modification is to force the XrdCl client in the client process to establish multiple TCP connections to the servers. By default the client will multiplex requests, including those for different files, over the same network connection. As of xrootd 5.1 (used at the time of the test) the server will only take and reply to one read request at a time from a single physical connection. (The details of this vary for vector read requests). A hypothesis is that for XCache, consisting of one or two disk nodes, this will make a larger difference compared to the case of a service like EOS with a larger number of disk nodes.

cms-skimmer

This test produces a mid-range data rate of up to 95 MB/s. The runs showed a range of CPU efficiency from 76.0% (EOS), 81.4% or 81.5% (XCache with HDD and SDD respectively) to 92.4% when reading data from the local filesystems. The jobs themselves contained a setup and compilation step followed by the data reading portion and the efficiency measurement covers the whole job. In cases where the device utilisation is available, it can be seen to be 3.7% or less. As an example the classification of CPU use on the machine running when the data are fetched from EOS is shown in Fig. 6.

Figure 6: Run of 64 concurrent *cms-skimmer* jobs on a 64 hardware threads machine, using EOS as data source. The top plot is the CPU utilisation and the bottom is the network interface usage.

top-xaod

This test was on the low end of the read rates, reaching only up to 13.6 MB/s. The CPU efficiency of the job was > 99% in all configurations tested.

Relationship between job performance and disk utilisation

Disk utilisation is defined in subsection 4.4 and it is the same quantity as reported by the system utility *iostat*. It is not clear how the utilisation figure might be applied in estimating achievable performance. Making such an estimate is discussed in the later subsection 4.6. Therefore an investigation of how the utilisation varies with load was made.

Several of the single threaded *cms-skimmer* runs were made, varying the number of concurrent jobs in the run. The jobs were run on a 64 hardware thread machine, varying the number of concurrent jobs within the run in various steps between 1 to 64. Each job accessed a different data file, via xrootd, from a plain xrootd server. On the server all data files had been placed on one 12 TB hard disk, with the same specification as described in 4.1. Before each run the page cache on the disk server was cleared. The results obtained are shown in table 10.

Concurrent jobs	Net (MB/s)	CPU eff (%)	rreq/s/dev	MB/s/dev	kB/rreq	util (%)
1	2.07	75.0	46.8	4.94	106	22.3
2	4.21	70.9	85.0	9.49	112	41.3
4	10.1	65.3	155	20.3	131	64.9
8	13.8	48.3	223	28.3	127	92.7
16	17.5	30.4	244	33.7	138	99.6
32	14.7	13.3	239	30.3	127	100
33	15.4	13.7	235	30.8	131	100
34	14.4	12.0	230	29.4	128	99.5
36	14.4	11.5	232	29.6	127	100
40	14.5	10.7	229	29.4	128	100
48	13.6	7.97	221	27.3	124	100
64	12.5	5.51	215	23.7	111	100

Table 10: Variable number of concurrent *cms-skimmer* jobs. Data are served from a single xrootd server, stored on a single hard disk and processed on a client machine with 64 hardware threads via the xrootd protocol. Shown is the overall incoming data rate at the client network interface, the CPU efficiency achieved, read requests per second, read rate, average read request size and disk utilisation of the data disk on the server.

In particular the achievable overall data rate received at the client against the disk utilisation is shown in Fig. 7. The relationship is roughly linear up to disk utilisations of about 90%. Once the utilisation reaches 100% there is a marginal rise in data rate followed by a fall. It is worth noting the definition of utilisation does not necessarily imply that the data rate can no longer rise once it reaches 100%.

Figure 7: The observed data disk utilisation against received data rate at a client running the *cms-skimmer* analysis.

Looking at the CPU efficiency against disk utilisation (Fig. 8) or network rate (Fig. 9) indicates this not a complete picture.

Figure 8: The observed job CPU efficiency against the data disk utilisation for the *cms-skimmer* analysis.

Figure 9: The observed job CPU efficiency against the received data rate for the *cms-skimmer* analysis.

From Fig. 8 it is clear that the CPU efficiency falls as the disk utilisation rises. Moreover, Fig. 9 shows two regions, one with a negative slope and one with a positive one. The positive slope region is where utilisation is saturated. It is proposed that in that region increasing concurrency will cause a fall in efficiency as the data rate no longer rises, while other effects also reduce the data rate.

The negative sloped region could be interpreted by assuming that while the network rate is growing due to increasing data requests, the efficiency falls due to other effects. These might be the same as in the positive sloped region and a possible explanation is that this is due to a rising request latency, although this theory has not been put yet to the test.

With the proposed model in mind it is expected that the relationships between the quantities discussed will vary between different types of job and with the type of storage device. Different jobs will have different patterns and number of I/O requests and storage devices will inherently perform in different ways. Jobs may also have different dependencies between processing and data fetching, e.g. issuing data fetch requests asynchronously while processing previously obtained data. Storage systems might have different dependencies between servicing requests, such as servicing certain type of requests on a single connection sequentially.

Summary

A comparison is made here between the three types of jobs previously discussed. Table 11 shows the read rate and read request rates per HDD device for XCache. Also shown is the observed CPU efficiency and – where available – the CPU efficiency seen when using EOS as the data source.

Job Type	MB/s/dev	rreq/s/dev	CPU eff (%)
agg-gradients	25	48	29
cms-skimmer	0.9	6	81 (76)
top-xaod	0.1	0.3	99 (99)

Table 11: Selected HDD-based results from tables 7, 8 and 9. In all three cases the rates and CPU efficiency on the HDD XCache are shown. Where available the CPU efficiency from an EOS based run is shown between parentheses.

From this comparison, one can see that the higher rate jobs had a lower CPU efficiency and a larger difference in the CPU efficiency between XCache and EOS.

4.6 Estimating of number of jobs supported by an XCache node

Here we can try to estimate of the number of jobs that could be sustained by Xcache instances composed of one 96-HDD or one 16-SSD node, with 25 Gb/s connectivity. The approach taken is to consider two limiting factors on the number of jobs, calculated after rescaling for a CPU efficiency of 100%. These factors are:

- the network interface rate limit on the storage server
- the storage device utilisation

name	network limit	100% util 96-HDD (16-SSD)
top-xaod	14000	41000 (20000)
cms-skimmer	1600	1800 (2800)
aggregate gradients	21	130 (61)

Table 12: The estimated number of client hardware threads for each type of analysis, assuming 100% CPU efficiency, that could be supported by one of the XCache instances used in the test. The limit is considered either due to a network limit of 2800 MB/s (approaching the 25Gbit/s interface limit) and at the hypothetical point at which the 96-HD or 16-SSD devices would be at 100% utilisation assuming the observed utilisation scales linearly.

The estimates are shown in table 12. A major limit of this estimate is the assumption of 100% CPU efficiency. This is linked to the analysis shown in section 4.5 concerning the change of CPU efficiency with increasing storage device utilisation. The impact of a CPU efficiency below 100% would be to increase the number of jobs which could be supported while approaching 100% utilisation, but at the cost of falling use of the client machines' CPUs. This factor could be 3 times as many jobs for the HDD case, at the cost of $\sim 30\%$ CPU efficiency. Conversely it may be desirable to target a utilisation well below 100% to reduce performance variation.

4.7 Conclusions of the data access performance tests

The observations shown in the hardware and baseline tests sections (4.1, 4.2) established the HDD request limits and observed that a higher aggregate read rate could be reached with a sequential workload rather than one with many seeks, as expected. The difference between sequential or high-seek was smaller with SSD based storage.

The focus then moved to three experiment analysis workloads, which showed a range of read rates. For the same type of storage (HDD) there is a trend that the higher read rate jobs had lower CPU efficiency. Where measured, the variation in CPU efficiency was also larger for the high rate jobs. Local storage had the highest CPU efficiency, followed by remote SSD and then HDD.

Investigation of the device utilisation metric for one type of analysis and using storage with one HDD showed an approximately linear relationship of the utilisation to data rate. Comparing observed CPU efficiency to utilisation rate also showed a relationship that appeared reasonably linear up to at least 65% utilisation. Similar studies for SSD based storage have not been done.

An estimate of the maximum number of client hardware threads for each type of analysis that each type of XCache instance can support has been made. Estimates were obtained assuming a 100% CPU efficiency and a 100% device utilisation. At the same time it has been measured that this is not the reality for the HDD case, at least. Therefore it is thought the estimates presented are a lower bound on the number of jobs which could be supported. In reality more can be supported, but with lower CPU efficiency, or fewer supported with less variation of performance. One possibility for better estimates may be to target a device utilisation and file placement that is thought reasonable for the storage system, and use sufficient clients in the test so that no extrapolation is needed.

It is thought that a theoretical model of the CPU efficiency could be made but it would be increasingly complex if it had to include the factors mentioned at the end of the job performance and utilisation discussion in section 4.5. It is not clear if trying to make this model is the best approach.

The meaning of CPU efficiency as a useful metric has not been discussed. CPU efficiency has the benefit that it is reasonably straightforward to calculate and is often recorded. The measurement is a reflection of what fraction of time the processes of a workload have been assigned to run. CPU efficiency says little about how effective the use of the CPU is. Measurements of instructions-per-cycle for some of the sample workloads were done, as recorded in tables 13 and 14 but no interpretation is given for them.

Config	IPC
Full machine	1.89
Single process	1.65

Table 13: Instructions per cycle for the *top-xaod* analysis, per involved core.

Config	IPC
Full machine	1.47
Single process	1.46

Table 14: Instructions per cycle for the *cms-skimmer* analysis, per involved core.

5 Conclusions and wrap-up

In 2021 we started an investigation in the area of physics analysis, with a clear focus on the CERN activities. The goal was to try to get a better view on the analysis landscape at CERN and whether there is the immediate need for resource investments of IT in this area. We followed two different directions:

- General analysis in the computer centre (section 3). The assumption here was that quite a few people are using LXPLUS/LXBATCH for their analysis activity reading data from EOS. An extensive log file investigation was done to identify patterns and possible bottlenecks.
- Dedicated high performance analysis (section 4). This was triggered by the physics analysis activities of Josh Bendavid from CMS. The IT department provided the CMG group with dedicated high performance and high throughput servers and several measurements were done by him and with input from the IT experts. Two additional servers were also provided to analysis experts in ATLAS.

With the release of this document, we would like to wrap up this investigation with these conclusions and actions:

- the existing hardware available in IT is generally able to handle current dedicated analysis activities and high performance/throughput servers can be requested by physics groups, with the approval of the computing coordinator and the IT resource manager;
- the investigation of the EOS and LXPLUS/LXBATCH logs show that the disk servers operate well below saturation and there is no evidence for the need of hardware/software improvements for almost all of the currently run applications;
- despite this investigations having concluded, we will keep using the mailing list `it-dep-cern-lhc-analysis-studies@cern.ch` for feedback and sharing observations;
- the IT department will internally continue systematic performance measurements of EOS-LXPLUS/LXBATCH and communicate any findings to the relevant people in the experiments;
- within the community new approaches to analysis are being discussed and explored. In order to better understand analysis use cases that are not “mainstream“ today but are considered important, now or in the near future, we look forward to directly interact with analysis users to discuss in detail their use cases. The experiments are encouraged to take a leading role in facilitating this exchange.

A EOS log file investigation - Bernd Panzer-Steindel

This note tries to look at the question whether there is significant physics analysis activity inside the CERN Tier-0 system and identify possible I/O bottlenecks.

Data for a 4-month period (February – May 2021) from EOS log files (ATLAS and CMS) containing each and every file access were investigated. The focus is on the read activity of the users. The log files also contain the EOS internal I/O activities (rebalance, error recovery, scrubbing, etc.), which are explicitly ignored in the following investigation.

First, some high level statistics for the mentioned 4-month period are summarised in table 15.

	ATLAS		CMS	
Total number of distinct users	1488		1416	
Amount of total data read [PB]	117.3	100%	169.2	100%
Data read from lxplus [PB]	8.3	7%	3.4	2%
Data read from batch [PB]	86.2	74%	103.5	61%
Data read from eosftp [PB]	17.7	15%	56.1	33%
Data read directly from external IPs [PB]	5.0	4%	6.2	4%

Table 15: Global read data volumes.

The plots in Fig. 10 show the data read and written per day for ATLAS and CMS. This daily I/O activity translates into average data rates for CMS and ATLAS of 16.3 GB/s and 11.3 GB/s respectively. The read over write ratio was about a factor 3-4.

Figure 10: Daily amounts of data read (blue) and written (orange) for ATLAS (upper plot) and CMS (lower plot).

The plots in Fig. 11 show the sorted total sum of data read per user over the 4-month investigation period.

Figure 11: Total data read by user, ranked, for ATLAS (upper plot) and CMS (lower plot).

Assuming that the physics analysis process results in a large I/O load, we made a cut at 100 TB read per user in the 4-month period (about 1 TB average read per working day). This reduces the number of “interesting” users from 1488 to 90 for ATLAS and from 1418 to 78 for CMS. In addition, several production users were removed from the data sets, e.g. ATLAS special users: atlas003, atlas001, atltzp1 (73 PB read) and CMS special users: cmsprd, cmsunified, cmst0, cmsbuild (56 PB).

The following four plots show the file access I/O speed distribution during the 4-month period for ATLAS and CMS. There are two plots with the same data for each ATLAS (Fig. 12) and CMS (Fig. 13) differing just by the cut-off on the I/O rate. The limit at 250 MB/s corresponds to the maximum performance of the disk models used in the ATLAS and CMS EOS pools. There is actually

a mix of disks with different performances (theoretically up to 280 MB/s for some of them). From the overflow one can then easily infer the number of reads using the memory cache of the disk servers. Currently ATLAS has an EOS pool size of 29 PB and CMS 30 PB. The default EOS space configuration is still using server mirroring and the total possible memory cache size on the servers is 18 TB for ATLAS and 16 TB for CMS.

Figure 12: Read speed distribution for “analysis” ATLAS users up to 1000 MB/s (upper plot) and up to 250 MB/s (lower plot).

Figure 13: Read speed distribution for “analysis” CMS users up to 1000 MB/s (upper plot) and up to 250 MB/s (lower plot).

The mean read performance values are low for ATLAS and CMS (8 MB/S and 16 MB/s respectively). There is a large effect from small read values, i.e. excluding read accesses lower than 10 MB would shift the mean value to 52 MB/s and 24 MB/s for ATLAS and CMS respectively. The read activity of the mentioned special users (e.g. atlas003, cmsprd) yields mean values of 62 MB/s (ATLAS) and 17 MB/s (CMS).

Less than 1% of the file reads can make use of the memory cache on the server. The peaks in the plots are due to some users processing the same file thousands of times in a very short period.

Table 16 describes the access patterns for the users which read more than 100 TB of data during the 4-month period (the “analysis users”). A lot of files were read multiple thousands of times. The number of re-read files is much larger for ATLAS than for CMS.

	ATLAS	CMS
Total number of "100 TB" users	87	74
Amount of total data read [PB]	40.2	107.8
Data read from LXPLUS [PB]	2.5	2.1
Data read from batch [PB]	37.5	92.3
Total size of unique files read [PB]	0.5	10.8
Number of unique files read [million]	0.7	5.3
Number of re-read files [million]	155	38.0

Table 16: Access patterns for the "heavy" users.

The high number of re-reads would suggest that an attached extra cache for EOS would be useful, but the measurements about the I/O speed tell a different story, as they show that the I/O generated by the applications is far less than the capabilities of the storage infrastructure.

The I/O read performance distributions are not very much different for different users, as can be seen from the plots in Fig. 14.

Figure 14: Read speed distributions for different “analysis” users, ranked by their mean I/O speed, for ATLAS (upper plot) and CMS (lower plot).

More than 97% of all opened files have a *.root* ending and looking at the access pattern of the higher level directories inside EOS shows indications that physics analysis was indeed done on this data by the selected “100 TB users”.

The ATLAS directory access structure has a total of 111 unique directories, and the top 20 correspond to 97% of file accesses within these directories (table 17).

Number of accesses	Directory name
11647372	/eos/atlas/atlascerngroupdisk/phys-higgs/HSG8
8104172	/eos/atlas/atlascerngroupdisk/phys-higgs/HSG4
2385553	/eos/atlas/atlaslocalgroupdisk/dq2/rucio
2209983	/eos/atlas/atlasgroupdisk/phys-hdbs/dq2
2198096	/eos/atlas/atlascerngroupdisk/phys-susy/bbMET_ANA-SUSY-2018-34
1857579	/eos/atlas/atlascerngroupdisk/phys-exotics/lpx
1729775	/eos/atlas/atlasgroupdisk/perf-tau/dq2
1552090	/eos/atlas/atlasgroupdisk/phys-top/dq2
1509974	/eos/atlas/user/a/ademaria
626199	/eos/atlas/atlascerngroupdisk/phys-higgs/HSG6
518265	/eos/atlas/atlascerngroupdisk/phys-sm/hmdy
475719	/eos/atlas/atlasgroupdisk/perf-flavtag/dq2
417052	/eos/atlas/atlasgroupdisk/phys-sm/rucio
324768	/eos/atlas/atlascerngroupdisk/phys-susy/DVjets_ANA-SUSY-2018-13
322110	/eos/atlas/unpledged/group-tokyo/users
268778	/eos/atlas/atlascerngroupdisk/phys-top/topxs
211812	/eos/atlas/user/l/longjon
210733	/eos/atlas/atlascerngroupdisk/phys-higgs/HSG3
191658	/eos/atlas/user/n/nbruscin
167310	/eos/atlas/atlascerngroupdisk/perf-jets/JETDEF

Table 17: Number of accesses for the 20 most accessed ATLAS directories.

Similarly, for CMS there are in total 239 unique directories, and the top 20 correspond to 96% of file access within these directories (table 18).

Number of accesses	Directory name
83210562	/eos/cms/store/group/phys_tau
29687932	/eos/cms/store/group/phys_heavyions
15834167	/eos/cms/store/group/phys_higgs
8489995	/eos/cms/store/cmst3/group
3206538	/eos/cms/store/group/phys_bphys
2785421	/eos/cms/store/group/phys_smp
1169675	/eos/cms/store/group/phys_susy
1039443	/eos/cms/store/group/phys_exotica
776222	/eos/cms/store/data/Run2017B
719283	/eos/cms/store/group/upgrade
696995	/eos/cms/store/group/phys_top
688189	/eos/cms/store/mc/RunIISummer20UL18RECO
678398	/eos/cms/store/mc/RunIISummer20ULPrePremix
451338	/eos/cms/store/mc/Phase2HLTTRSummer20ReRECOMiniAOD
436179	/eos/cms/store/group/phys_jetmet
415160	/eos/cms/store/hidata/PARun2016C
387685	/eos/cms/store/cmst3/user
331784	/eos/cms/store/mc/RunIISummer20UL17RECO
326365	/eos/cms/store/group/dpg_ecal
312093	/eos/cms/store/user/georgia

Table 18: Number of accesses for the 20 most accessed CMS directories.

As shown before, the average file read speed is about 16 MB/s and 7 MB/s for CMS and ATLAS respectively. The EOS hardware setup (server models, HDD models, network, etc.) is the same for ATLAS and CMS, thus the low average file access speed of these experiments cannot be due to hardware limitations.

A set of more detailed measurements of the average file read speed was done after selecting only reads bigger than 10 MB and lasting more than one second; this reduces the amount of data by a factor 10 and 6 for ATLAS and CMS respectively, but the reduction in wall time is negligible. The average read rates are summarised in table 19. It was also checked that these numbers do not differ significantly for users who read between 10 and 100 TB in the reference period.

Conditions	ATLAS		CMS	
	Read rate (MB/s)	No. of reads	Read rate (MB/s)	No. of reads
All data, no cuts	7.3	$221 \cdot 10^6$	15.4	$316 \cdot 10^6$
All data	37.3	$38 \cdot 10^6$	29.6	$154 \cdot 10^6$
xrootd	86.0	$2 \cdot 10^6$	24.7	$53 \cdot 10^6$
fuse	34.5	$36 \cdot 10^6$	32.2	$100 \cdot 10^6$
vector reads	2.0	$1 \cdot 10^5$	1.2	$2.7 \cdot 10^6$
eoscp	7.0	200	121	$47 \cdot 10^3$

Table 19: Average read rates, global and by protocol, for reads done by “analysis” users, of more than 10 MB and lasting more than one second.

To further proof that any I/O limits are caused by the application software

and not the data storage infrastructure, a special I/O “benchmark” was conducted. Several thousands of batch jobs were run containing just a simple I/O program reading files and calculating the I/O speed. The files were sampled randomly from the list of files accessed during the mentioned measuring period by ATLAS and CMS. The access was via the EOS FUSE interface on the batch nodes. The read speed distributions for the benchmark jobs are plotted in Fig. 15.

Figure 15: Read speed distributions for the benchmark jobs run on ATLAS (upper plot) and CMS (lower plot) files.

In addition to this simple file read exercise, the ATLAS files were also used to copy files to the local batch directory instead of reading into the memory of the benchmark application. This was done using eoscp and not the EOS FUSE interface (Fig. 16). The mean value is even higher, 99 MB/s compare to 83 MB/s.

Figure 16: Read speed distributions for the benchmark jobs run on ATLAS files when the file is locally to the worker node using eoscp.

The results shown in the previous three plots show clearly that much higher data rates are possible and thus the data storage infrastructure is not responsible for the measured lower data rates of ATLAS and CMS. It is also clear that the access patterns may differ considerably between these simple benchmarks and the real applications.

The total data rates during the 4-month period in the ATLAS and CMS EOS pools were, as mentioned before, 11 GB/s and 16 GB/s with peaks up to 30 GB/s. The achievable throughput in the two EOS pools is at the level of 250 GB/s each, network limited due to the used network NICs (pure HDD speed could theoretically exceed 1 TB/s of aggregate bandwidth).

The plots in Fig. 17 show that the file size distribution is pretty much the same between ATLAS and CMS.

Figure 17: Distributions of the size of read files for ATLAS (upper plot) and CMS (lower plot).

The plots in Fig. 18 represent the distributions of the file opens per second. The curves show that 85% of the entries for CMS and 70% of the entries for ATLAS correspond to less than 20 per file opens per second. The shape of the distributions for very high file opens per second shows that there is no principle limitation.

Figure 18: Distributions of the file opens per second for ATLAS (upper plot) and CMS (lower plot).

One would presume that file seeks are typical of a physics analysis process. The plots in Fig. 19 depict the number of forward seeks per file access. For CMS 60% of all accesses have under 10 seeks per file, while the number for ATLAS is 94%. This seems to indicate that ATLAS uses local file copies also for the physics analysis jobs.

Figure 19: Distributions of the file seeks per second for ATLAS (upper plot) and CMS (lower plot).

The majority of file accesses for these “100 TB” users went through the batch system during the 4-month time period.

- CMS: 5.7M jobs, 245K days of wallclock time = 20.4 KHS06 (4% of the 500 KHS06 pledge)
- ATLAS: 1.6M jobs, 54K days wallclock time = 5 KHS06 (1% of the 525 KHS06 pledge)

The distributions of the batch job efficiencies for the “100 TB” users in the reference period are shown in Fig. 20.

Figure 20: Distributions of the batch job efficiencies for ATLAS (upper plot) and CMS (lower plot).

The overflows correspond to users spawning multiple processes within the batch jobs without requesting multiple cores in the batch system. The batch log files are not able to provide information for the specific queue names of the experiments, e.g. analysis queues.

A very preliminary look into measuring disk contention was given by taking all CMS read accesses from a particular day and measuring the number of concurrent reads per second per disk in the CMS EOS instance (which includes 143 servers with 48-96 disks each). In figure 21 one can see an average over all disks of the fraction of time during which there was a given number of concurrent streams. It is planned to further investigate how disk contention correlates with performance.

Figure 21: Average fraction of time (in percent) during which the number of concurrent streams on a storage server hard drive had a given value. The plot refers to EOSCMS on May 31 2021.

HL-LHC lookout

We assume as a start a similar scheme for the Tier-0 storage mix in 2028 and today (RAW, EOD, AOD mixed) and a resource request of 500 PB HDD storage each for ATLAS and CMS. The disk server architecture is most likely not going to change radically, i.e. one front-end CPU server with several JBOD arrays (~ 100 HDDs per server). We assume a disk size of 30 TB based on some extrapolation summarised in Fig. 22 and a memory size of 512 GB.

Figure 22: Projected evolution of the HDD sizes.

During the next five years we will most likely move from a fully mirrored space setup to a mixture of erasure coding and two copies of the data (raw-data/usable-data $\simeq 1.5$). 500 PB of storage would then translate into roughly 260 servers with a total memory of 130 TB and the number of spindles would be about a factor two higher than today. The maximum I/O speed per spindle would increase from today's 280 MB/s to about 500 MB/s. The total I/O throughput of each of the EOS pools would be of the order 1 TB/s.

Conclusion

There seems to be no performance bottleneck in the activities of the identified “analysis” users. The storage infrastructure (server, network, etc.) has still a high headroom to cope with an increase in performance requirements. Thus, there is currently no need to introduce extra caching layers or performance enhanced EOS sub-pools (keyword: QoS, SSD layers).

It would be good to have this type of investigation automatised and integrated into the monitoring, to produce these histograms in a regular manner.

Changelog

- 07/03/22. Version 1.0. Initial version

References

- [1] D. Smith, A. Sciabà, Artificial load generation for xcache and reduction of application write delay. *CHEP* (2019) <https://indico.cern.ch/event/773049/contributions/3474478/> [accessed 2021-11-16]
- [2] J. Bendavid, High-performance machines for interactive analysis: Update *IT R&D advisory group meeting*. Wednesday 24 Feb 2021. <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1005976/> [accessed 2021-11-16]
- [3] Automated XRD_PARALLELEVTLOOP settings *XRootD project github repository issue tracker* <https://github.com/xrootd/xrootd/issues/1425> [accessed 2021-11-16]
- [4] S. Mete, G. Stewart, prmon: Process Monitor *GDB Meeting*. 9 September 2020. https://indico.cern.ch/event/813751/contributions/3991506/attachments/2099462/3529369/prmon_mete.pdf [accessed 2021-11-16]